

Disease resistance

Resistance of rice breeding lines to bacterial blight (BB) and stem rot (SR)

D. V. S. Panwar, M. P. Bansal, H. Chand, and M. R. Naidu, Haryana Agricultural University (HAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kaul 132021, Haryana, India

We screened 91 genotypes with short to medium durations for reaction to BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye (leaf blight and kresek phase) and SR *Sclerotium oryzae* Cattaneo during 1984 wet season.

Each entry was planted in two 5-m-long rows, at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with BB

suspension at 21 d after transplanting (DT) for kresek and at 45 DT for leaf blight and scored at 30 and 14 d after inoculation. For screening for SR resistance, entries were planted in an infected plot and disease incidence recorded at maturity.

The leaf blight and kresek phases differed. Only 10 lines showed resistance to the kresek stage, but 30 showed resistance to the leaf blight phase.

HAU1 18-104, HKR120, CR294-548, and DV85 had resistance to both kresek and leaf blight phases (see table). Only HKR120 showed resistance to both phases of BB and to SR. HAU118-104, HAU118-154, HAU118-726, HAU83-164, RP2151-21-1, and TKM6 showed resistance to two problems and moderate resistance to one. These lines (except TKM6 and DV85) also have desirable agronomic traits. □

Reaction of rice lines to SR, and the kresek and leaf blight phases of BB in the field at HAU, RRS, Haryana, India, 1984 wet season.

Entry	Parentage	Days to 50% heading	Reaction ^a to		
			Kresek	Leaf blight	Stem rot
HAU118-104	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	109	R	R	MR
HAU118-106	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	104	MS	R	R
HAU118-111	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	106	R	MR	MR
HAU118-154	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	106	MR	R	R
HAU118-187	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	107	MR	R	MR
HAU118-726	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	104	R	MR	R
HAU118-788	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2// IR5853-162-1-2	108	MR	R	MR
HKR120	Ptb 33/4* IR3403-267-1	111	R	R	R
HKR122	Ptb 33/4* IR3403-267-1	115	MR	R	MR
HAU83-38	SFCIII/Basmati 370	106	MS	R	MR
HAU83-164	SFCIII/Basmati 370	122	MR	R	R
HAU83-222	SFCIII/Basmati 370	119	MR	R	MR
RP2151-21-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	110	MR	R	R
RP2151-224-4	IET4141/CR98-7216	122	MR	MR	R
RP2151-173-1-8	IET4141/CR98-7216	110	MR	R	MR
IET4141	IR8/BJ143//IR22	112	MS	R	R
IR54	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88// IR2061-214-3-6	121	MR	R	MR
CR3 19-644	-	110	MR	R	MR
CR294-548	-	108	R	R	MS
Govind	IR20/IR24	86	MR	R	MR
IR9784-142-1-3	IR1632-93-2-2/IR5534	101	MS	R	MR
IR13420-6-3-3	IR2863-38-1/2* IR36	109	MR	R	MR
TKM6	-	115	MR	R	R
DV85	-	92	R	R	S

^aR = resistant (score of 3 or lower), MR = moderately resistant (5), MS = moderately susceptible (7), and S = susceptible.

Field reaction of IR varieties to rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses

A. Muis, M. Sudjak S, A. Bastian, S. Sama, and A. Hasanuddin, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P. O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia; and R. C. Cabunagan and H. Hibino, IRR

IR varieties planted in monthly planting trials in the experimental field at Maros and in the RTV nursery at Lanrang substation, South Sulawesi, were used to assess incidence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) Aug-Oct 1986. Leaf samples were collected from 10 plants of each variety at 30 and at 45 d after transplanting (DT) and indexed by latex test.

RTBV and RTSV incidence varied with month of planting (Table 1).

Regardless of variety, virus incidence was higher in plots planted the last wk

Table 1. RTBV and RTSV incidence at 45 DT in 10 varieties planted on 1 Aug, 30 Aug, and 1 Oct, 1986, Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Planting date	Variety	Plants ^a (%) with	
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV
1 Aug 1986	IR26	0	10
	IR30	0	30
	IR42	30	0
	IR54	10	20
	IR58	0	0
	IR60	0	0
	IR62	0	0
	IR64	0	0
	TN1	70	0
	30 Aug	IR26	10
IR30		20	40
IR42		70	0
IR54		70	0
IR58		20	0
IR60		10	0
IR62		10	0
IR64		20	0
TN1		100	0
1 Oct		IR26	0
	IR30	30	10
	IR42	80	10
	IR54	30	10
	IR5	80	10
	IR6	00	0
	IR62	0	0
	IR64	10	10
	TN1	100	0

^aNo variety showed RTSV infection only.